

OCCURRENCE OF MYCOTOXINS IN ASPERGILLUS TAMARII-INFECTED WILD CASTOR SEEDS IN STORAGE

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ABSTRACT

Castor seeds are obtained from the castor plant (*Ricinus communis L.*) of the family Euphorbiaceae. The plant is important because of the high oil content (40 – 57%) of the seeds. Basically, the oil is obtained by pressing or solvent extraction methods. Although castor oil is used for frying, it has almost unlimited industrial applications and enjoys tremendous world demand in the pharmaceutical, paint, cosmetics, textile, leather, lubricant, chemical, plastic, fiber, automobile and engineering industries. Also, it has the advantage over other oils because it is a renewable resource, biodegradable and eco-friendly. Many derivatives that have a similar chemical composition as petroleum-based oil can be produced from castor oil. The pomace is used for fertilizer and when detoxified by heating at 140°C for 20 minutes, it can be used as an ingredient for feed formulation. Today, castor is cultivated in not less than thirty countries on commercial scales. Eight samples of clean wild castor seeds were collected from stores in two locations (Kabba and Ankpa) in Kogi state of Nigeria. *Aspergillus tamarii* previously isolated from naturally infected wild castor seeds in storage was artificially introduced into the seed samples and were incubated at room temperature (27±1°C) for a storage period of 180 days. At sixty days interval, samples were analyzed and purified using a multi-toxin thin layer chromatography method and gas chromatography coupled with mass spectrophotometry. The result showed occurrence of some mycotoxins in five out of the 8 treated seed samples. This suggested that *Aspergillus tamarii* produced certain unknown mycotoxins with Rf values of 0.27, 0.69, 0.30, 0.61, and 0.37 respectively, using toluene : ethylacetate : formic acid . The gas chromatographic and mass spectrometric spectra of detected metabolites did not correspond to those of the standard mycotoxins screened available. The compounds in the tested samples were different from the standard mycotoxins with respect to molecular weight of both the mother ions and component fragments. The toxicity and chemical characteristics of mycotoxins produced by *Aspergillus tamarii* on castor seeds requires further investigation. Some of the characteristics of these mycotoxins include but not limited to chemical stability, structural diversity, heat stability, carcinogenicity, nephrotoxicity, neurotoxicity, mutagenicity, teratogenicity, cytotoxicity.

KEYWORDS: castor seeds, *Aspergillus tamarii*, mycotoxin, storage, occurrence.

INTRODUCTION

Prior to harvest, grains and oil seeds are protected greatly from mould infection by their hard shells. However, endosperm may be attacked by mould if the shells are dented or damaged before harvest. Following harvest, the defense mechanism of grains and oil seeds against fungal invasion decreases (Annor *et al.*, 2004) and therefore, fungal population may increase and subsequently result in the production of secondary metabolites (mycotoxins) during drying, processing and storage (Hell *et al.*,2009)

Mould growth and mycotoxin production in grains and oil seeds and other agro-allied commodities are very important to producers, processors and consumers of such commodities (CAST, 2003). Mycotoxins are low molecular weight toxic compounds produced by certain toxigenic strains of a variety of filamentous fungi under favorable conditions (such as temperature and moisture) and all over the world, they cause enormous economic losses annually to the grain and oil seed trade and marketing (Cardwell *et al.*,2001; Windels, 2000).

According to the World Bank report (1993), diseases caused by mycotoxins lead to reduced life expectancy in developing countries (Bankole *et al.*, 2008) and 40% of the productivity lost to diseases in developing countries is due to diseases exacerbated by mycotoxins, especially aflatoxins (Doctor fungus, 2008; Bhat and Miller, 2010).

Regrettably, many people in the developing countries are not even aware of the effect of consuming or exposure to mould infected products. However, consumers in the developed world are now aware of effect of these toxins and will stay away from products that contain mycotoxins beyond the acceptance level and the European Union (EU) has pegged a regulatory limit of 3hg/kg for ochratoxin and 2hg/kg for aflatoxins.

Due to the EU regulatory limit, export of agricultural products particularly groundnut from African countries have dropped in recent years (Bhat and Vashanti, 2001; Otzuki *et al.*, 2001). According to World Bank estimate, the EU policy will reduce imports of cereals, dry fruits n nuts from nine African countries by 64% and this will cost African counties about US \$670 million in trade per year (Kellerhal, 2000). Some mycotoxins are known to be either carcinogenic oestrogenic, neurotoxic, nephrotoxic, dematotoxic, mutagenic and immuno suppressive (Agag, 2005; Paul *et al.*, 2001). The Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) of the United Nations has estimated that 25% of the world food crops are contaminated by mycotoxins each year (Dahman-Levinson *et al.*, 2006).

Castor seed is an important oil-rich seed. The seed are consumed as condiments in Nigerian soup especially in the eastern part of Nigeria (Uzogara *et al.*, 1990); Onyeike and Acheru, 2002). The seeds contain 40 – 55% oil, 16 – 18% protein and 23.1 27.2% crude fiber, 20 – 23% ash and 3 – 7% (NFE) and it is high in phosphorous (Gobin *et al.*, 2001; Onyeike and Acheru, 2002).

Fungi of the genus *Aspergillus* are widely distributed storage fungi of grains and oil seeds and a number of them produce toxic metabolites (mycotoxins) including aflotoxins (Aboaba and Amasike, 1991; Bankole *et al.*, 1991, Bankole, 1993). *A. tamari* which is in the same taxonomic group with *Aspergillus flavus* has been isolated from naturally infected castor seeds in storage in Kogi State (Negedu *et al.*, 2006). Mycotoxins have been reported in some Nigerian oil seeds and nuts such as groundnut (McDonald, 1964); tiger nuts (Akano and Atanda, 1990); melon seed (Bankole and Jola, 2004).

In addition to economic losses, mycotoxins are potential health hazards (Gbodi *et al.* 1986; 2001). Therefore, the objective of the present study was to evaluate the mycotoxin producing ability of *Aspergillus tamarii* in castor seeds during storage.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The multi-toxin thin layer chromatographic method described by Gbodi *et al.* (1986) was used. Shortly after harvesting, sun-drying and bagging of wild castor seeds by farmers, about 1kg of seeds of two popular types (large and small seeded) were randomly collected from two locations in Kogi State of Nigeria. From the seed lots, 200g each of apparently clean seeds were dispensed into 8 autoclavable, plastic bottles of same materials, size and volume. Four bottles each of the seed types were prepared. The bottles were plugged with cotton wool and capped with aluminum foil and autoclaved at 121°C and 1.05cm² for 15 minutes. The bottles were cooled and the aluminum foil removed. The inoculum was a pure culture of *Aspergillus tamarii* previously isolated from naturally infected wild castor seeds in Kogi State (Negedu *et al.*, 2006). The inoculum was maintained for five days on Sabouraud Dextrose Agar (SDA) medium complemented with chloramphenicol (100mg/L) in Petri-dishes.

Artificial Inoculation

One disc (5mm diameter) of mycelium and agar of the inoculum was aseptically introduced into three bottles of large- and small-castor seed types and one bottle each of the seed types was left as control. Each bottle containing autoclaved, inoculated seeds plus one bottle of autoclaved uninoculated seeds constituted a treatment. Each treatment was replicated three times. All the bottles were kept at room temperature (27 – 30°C) for six months.

Mycotoxin extraction from samples

Fifty grams of Hammer mill pulverized sample was weighed into 500ml Erlenmeyer flask. Twenty-five milliliters of 1M phosphoric acid and twenty-five milliliters of methylene chloride were added. The flask was shaken for thirty minutes in a rotary shaker and the contents filtered with 3cm wide rapid filter paper in a Buchner funnel. At least 200ml of the filtrate was collected. Fifty milliliters aliquots were placed into separate 100ml. Erlenmeyer flasks and were evaporated to dryness in a water bath at 60°C.

For assay of mycotoxins, the dried extracted was re-dissolved in 250ml chloroform, centrifuged for 30 minutes and ten milliliter vials and evaporated just to dryness. The residue was re-dissolved in 200ml benzene: acetonitrile (98:2v/v) and shaken thoroughly for thirty seconds to ensure complete dissolution of toxins.

Chromatographic running of the extracted mycotoxin

Pre-coated chromatographic plates (20cm x20cm silica gel) were used and each plate was activated at 110°C for thirty minutes before use and prior to spotting, the prepared stock solutions of the standard toxins were thoroughly shaken twice.

On the chromatographic plate, at 2cm from the bottom, 5ml of the re-dissolved extracts were spotted using a 10µl glass syringe (Unimetrics, Shore wood, Illinois, 60436, USA). Beside the sample spots, on the same plate, 5µl of the standard mycotoxins (aflatoxin B1 and B2, ochratoxin) were spotted at 2cm from the bottom of the plate. Eight sample extracts were spotted each time.

Development of chromatographic plate

Prior to the development of the plate, the appropriate developing solvent (toluene: ethylacetate : formic acid (60:40:1 v/v) previously prepared was shaken and poured into a thin layer chromatographic tank (TLC) to about 1–5cm depth. Each plate was developed by standing it in the chromatographic tank containing the developing solvent to the depth not more than 1cm and developed until the solvent front was at least 3cm from the top of the plate. The solvent front was immediately marked as he distance moved by the mobile phase and recorded.

Detection of mycotoxins in the sample extracts

The developed plate was allowed to dry and examined visually under ultraviolet light. The fluorescent intensities of the sample sports and those of the standards were compared and recorded together with the aliquot volumes that were spotted. The retention factor (Rf) of the standard and that of sample sports were calculated as the “ratio of distance moved by the solute to that of the distant moved by the solvent front.

The mycotoxin in the sample extracts was detected by matching the fluorescence colour, intensities and the Rf values of the sample spots with those of the standard spots. Sample spots whose fluorescence intensities, colour and Rf values matched those of the standards were presumptively considered positive and used for confirmation.

Confirmation of mycotoxin presence

The TLC plates that were presumptively considered positive were sprayed firstly dried and viewed again at 365nm to confirm the presence of aflatoxin (a yellow fluorescence colour would confirms aflatoxin.

To confirm the presence of ochratoxin, the plates were sprayed with alcoholic aluminum chloride (20g/100ml alcohol) and by exposure of the plate to NH₃ vapour and viewed at 254nm. Change in colour from blue-green to bright blue florescence confirms ochratoxin.

Gas Chromatography/Mass Spectrometry (GC/MS)

Gas chromatographic/Mass spectrometric analysis was carried out as described by Jestoi *et al.* (2004). The GC was used to further separate and purify the various components of the extract before injection into the MS for deconvolution into separate components which was then compared against a library database of compounds.

To identify the unknown compounds, the test samples were subjected to GC/MS. The marked spots on the TLC plates were scrapped and dissolved in 2ml benzene: acetonitrile (98:2, v/v), shaken vigorously for 30 minutes and centrifuged. This process was repeated three times and the supernatants were combined, evaporated, reconstituted and used for GC/MS analysis.

The conditions of the GC were: capillary column 30mm x 50mm id); 0.1mm film thickness, helium gas (as carried gas) at flour rate of 35cm/sec; injector and transfer temperature at 20°C to hold for 30 minutes; 1.0hl of test solution and chemstation soft ware (GC: Agilent Technologies, U. S. A 6890N, Network GC system, version N.0.5.05).

The conditions of MS were: emission current 0.47MA, election energy 23^ev; scan from 60 to 650amu at the rate of 1.05s/scan. Acquisition is started when GC temperature reaches 200°C. (MS: Agilent Technologies, USA, 5973; Network Mass Selective Detector).

The identity of the unknown compound was matched with a list of compound in the database and some very close compounds were suggested based on molecular weight and the fragmentation pattern of such compounds into components.

RESULTS

The result of the multi-thin layer chromatographic analysis of benzene: acetonitrile extract of fungal infested castor seeds compared with that of the standard mycotoxins are presented in Table 1.

Extracts of three small-seeded samples fluoresced green colour under ultra violet light with Rf values of 0.27, 0.69 and 0.30 respectively at 365nm. Same colour remained unchanged when sprayed with alcoholic aluminium chloride solution to confirm ochratoxin, even after exposure to ammonia and viewed under UV light. No fluorescence was detected under the UV light when chromatogram of the extract of the un-inoculated small-seeded samples (control) was viewed under ultra violet light.

Under the ultraviolet light at 365nm, standard aflatoxins B1 and B2 fluoresced yellowish green colour of high intensity at Rf values of 0.70 and 0.64 respectively. Ochratoxin standard fluoresced green colour of low intensity with Rf value of 0.81 at 365nm, but the same colour became brighter under short wave. All the extracts from fungal infected small-seeded samples fluoresced under UV light at 365nm while no fluorescence was observed in the extract of the control (un-inoculated sample).

Two of the three extracts from large-seeded samples fluoresced green colour of low intensity with Rf values of 0.61 and 0.37 respectively when viewed under UV light at 365nm (Plate1). When sprayed with aqueous sulphuric acid solution (50% (50/50, v/v), to confirm the aflatoxin, the colour remained unchanged. Also, no

Colour was observed when sprayed with alcoholic aluminium chloride solution ((20g/100ml alcohol) to confirm ochratoxin under UV light.

The standard mycotoxins (aflatoxins B1 and B2 and ochratoxin), in comparison with the tested sample extracts produced green colours with Rf values of 0.64 and 0.76 respectively.

DISCUSSION

The fact that fluorescence bands corresponding to aflatoxins (B1 and B2) and ochratoxin were not observed when the chromatographic plate were viewed under the U. V light indicated that the fluorescence detected were metabolites that did not correspond to these standard mycotoxins available. However, the inoculated fungus (*Aspergillus tamarii*) could have produced one or more other secondary metabolites, different from the standard mycotoxins, since a fungus can produce mixtures of secondary metabolites. This reasoning agreed with Anton *et al.*(2004) who reported the production of a mixture of mycotoxins (enniatins, beauvericin and fusaproliferin) by *Fusarium avenaceum*. Hence, compounds whose fluorescence colour intensities and retention factors (Rf) values differ from those of the available mycotoxin standards were observed in the sample extracts.

The non-detection of fluorescence in one of the fungal-infected, large-seeded samples indicated absence of any mycotoxin in the sample which agreed with Gbodi *et al* (1986) who reported that maize seed inoculated with *Aspergillus flavus* and *Aspergillus parasiticus* were not contaminated with mycotoxins and Ibrahim *et al* (1998) who also reported the non contamination of Egyptian sorghum with mycotoxins after infection with *Aspergillus* species. The absence of the mycotoxin in the sample could be attributed to the fact that the species might have lost the ability to produce mycotoxin during the storage (Vinokuaova *et al.*, 2003). Also, it has been reported that the amount or presence of a fungus in a substrate is not necessarily indicative of the presence or level of mycotoxin production (Wiseman and Math, 1983).

CONCLUSION

The study showed that *Aspergillus tamarii* produced one or more secondary metabolites other than aflatoxins (B1 and B2) and ochratoxin in stored castor seeds. Further characterization of the metabolites could not be done due to limitations by standard mycotoxins availability.

REFERENCES

- Aboaba, O.O and Amasike, J (1991) Storage of melon seeds. *Nigerian Journal of Botany* 4: 213-219.
- Agag,B.I (2005) Mycotoxins in foods and feeds: 5-Trichothecenes A-T-2 Toxin. *Ass.Univ. Bull.Environ.Res.* 8(2): 107-124.
- Akano, D.A and Atanda, O.O (1990). The present level of aflatoxin in Nigerian groundnut cake (“Kuli-Kuli”) *Letters in Applied Microbiology*, 10:187-189.
- Annor,G.; Afoakwa, E.O and Sakyi-Dawson, E (2004). “Mycotoxin contamination in fermented foods: The present situation in West Africa”. *The conference on food safety under extreme conditions*,Jaen,Spain.Sep.2004. <http://works.bepress.com/georgeamponsahannor/1>
- Anton, P., Kristof, C., Broberg, A., Stenlid, J., Stenstrom, E. and Kenne, L. (2004). Enniatins of *Fusarium* sp. Strain F31 and their inhibition of *Botrytis cinerea* spore germination. *Journal of Natural Products*, 67: 851-857.
- Atawodi, S.E.; Atiku, A. and Lamorde,A.G. (1994). Aflatoxin contamination of Nigeria foods and feedstuffs. *Food Chemical Toxicology* 32: 61-63
- Bankole, S.A (1993). Moisture content, mould invasion and seed germinability of stored melon seeds. *Mycopathologia*. 122: 123-126.
- Bankole, S.A and Joda, A.O (2004). Effect of lemon grass (*Cymbopogon citratus* Stapf.) powder and essential oil on mould deterioration and aflatoxin contamination of melon seed (*Colosynthis citrulus* L.) *African Journal of Biotechnology*. 3: 52-59.
- Bankole, S., Schollenberger, M and Drochner, W (2008).Mycotoxins in food systems in Sub-Saharan Africa : A review *Mycotoxin Research* 22 (3): 163-169.
- Bhat , R.V and Miller, J.D (2010). Mycotoxins and food supply. FAO Corporate Document Repository. Sourced: <http://www.fao.org/docrep/u3550t/u3550t0e.htm> 1/25/2010
- Bhat, R.V and Vashanti, S (1999). Occurrence of aflatoxins and its economic impact on human nutrition and animal feed. The new regulation. *Agricultural Development* No. 23: 50-56.
- Cardwell, K.F.; Desjardins ,S.H., Munkold, G and Rubens, J (2001) Mycotoxins: The cost of achieving food safety and food quality. APSnet Feature story. Ed. Elliot, M.L. August 2001. <http://www.apsnet.org/online/feature/mycotoxin/>
- CAST (2003). Council for Agricultural Science and Technology, Ames, IOWA, U.S.A Mycotoxins. Risks in plant animals and human systems. *Task Force Report* 139 January, 2003.
- Dahmen-Levinson, U., Levinson, S. Mallwitz, F. and Abdallah, N. (2006). Fluorescence polarization - a rapid and reliable technique to quantify the Mycotoxin contamination study for zearalenone (ZON). PP 104. *Book of Abstracts*, International Conference on “Advances on genomics, biodiversity and rapid systems for detection of toxigenic fungi and mycotoxins” September 26-29, 2006. Monopoli (Bari), Italy. P 37. Retrieved from <http://www.Ispa.onr.n/mycoglobe-2006>.

- Doctor fungus (2008). Environmental moulds in the home FAQ and sick building syndrome. www.doctorfungus.org. (accessed 2008)
- Gbodi, T.A., Makun, H.A., Kabiru, Y.A., Ogbadoyi, E., Tijani, S.A., Lawal, S.A. and Bayero, R.A. (2001) Effect of local processing methods on aflatoxin contents of some common Nigerian foods prepared from artificially contaminated maize, rice and sorghum. *Journal of Agricultural Science*. Mansoura University. 26: 3759 -3769.
- Gbodi, T.A., Nwude, N., Aliu, Y.O and Ikediobi, C.O (1986) The mycoflora and some mycotoxins found in maize (*Zea mays*) in Plateau State of Nigeria. *Veterinary and Human Toxicology* 28 : 1-5.
- Gobin, A.M.I., Uguru, M.I and Deckers, I (2001). *Oil crops*. In: Crop production in tropical Africa. (Ed)Romain H. Raemackers, CIP Royal Library, Brussels. Pp 726-733
- Hell, K.; Gnonlonfin, B.G.J.; Kodjogbe, G.; Lamboni, Y and Abdourhamane, I.K (2009). Mycoflora and occurrence of aflatoxin in dried vegetables in Benin, Mali and Togo, West Africa. *International Journal of Food Microbiology*. 135 (2): 99-104.
- Ibrahim, F., Thanaa, A., El-Abedeem, Z., El-Morsy, G.A and El-Azhary, T.M (1998). Aflatoxins in Egyptian Sorghum grains: Detection and Estimation. *Egyptian Journal of Agricultural Research*, 76: 923-931.
- Jestoi, M. (2004). Emerging *Fusarium* Mycotoxins in Finland. Ph. D. Thesis. Department of Applied Chemistry and Microbiology, University of Helsinki, Finland. PP. 122.
- Kellerhal, F.M (2000). *Climate and crop distribution*. In: Principles of field crop production, Sydney University Press, Sydney. Pp. 64-94.
- Negedu, A. (2009) Fungal deterioration of castor (*Ricinus communis* L.) seeds grown in Kogi state, Nigeria. (unpublished). Ph .D. Thesis, Ahmadu Bello University , Zaria p. 290
- Onyeike, E.N. and Acheru, G.N. (2002) Chemical composition of selected Nigerian oilseeds and physicochemical properties of the oil extracts. *Food Chemistry*. 77: 431-437.
- Otzuki, T., Wilson, J.S. and Sewadeh, M. (2001). What price precaution? European harmonization of aflatoxin regulations and African groundnut exports. *European Review of Agricultural Economics* 28: 263-283.
- Paul, K. C., Nceba, G., Michael, F. D. and Anil, A.C. (2001). Exposure of rural and urban population in Kwazulu Natal, South Africa to fumonisin B in maize. *Environmental Health Perspective*. 109: 253-260.
- Uzogora, S.G., Agu, L.N. and Uzogora, E.O. (1990). A review of traditional fermented foods condiments and beverages in Nigeria: their benefits and possible problems. *Ecology of food and Nutrition*. 24: 267-288.
- Vinokurova, N.G., Ozerskaya, S.M., Baskunov, B.P. and Arinbasarov, M.U. (2003). The *Penicillium commune* Thom and *Pencillium clavigerum* Demelius fungi producing fumigaclavines A and B. *Microbiology*, 72: 149-151.
- Voss, A.K.; Riley, T.R.; Snook, M.E and Gelieneau-Van Waes, J (2009). Reproductive and sphigolipid metabolic effects of fumonisin B1 and its alkaline hydrolysis products in LL/Bc Mice: Hydrolyzed fumonisin B1 did not cause neuronal tube defects. *Toxicological Sciences* 112 (2): 459-467
- Windels, C.E (2000). Economic and Social impacts of *Fusarium* head blight: Changing farms and rural communities in the Northern great plains. *Phytopathology*. 90: 17-21.
- Wiseman, O.W. and Marth, E.H (1983). Behaviour of aflatoxin M₁ in yogurt, buttermilk and kefir. *Journal of Food Protection* 46: 115-116.

Table 1: Developed chromatogram of benzene: acetonitrile extract of *Aspergillus tamarii*-infected castor seeds under ultra violet light

	Standard Mycotoxins			Tested samples of small- seeded replicates				Tested Samples of large- seeded replicates			
	Aflatoxin B1	Aflatoxin B2	Ochratoxin	Control	1	2	3	Control	1	2	3
Rf Values	0.71	0.64	0.81	ND	0.27	0.69	0.30	ND	0.61	0.37	Not detected
Solute Volume (µl)	20	5	15	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10
Solute Concentration (µg/ml)	1000	100	10	Not detected	X	X	X	Not detected	X	X	X
Solute Distance (cm)	9.8	8.9	11.4	Not detected	3.8	9.6	3.5	Not detected	6.5	5.2	Not detected
Solvent front (cm)	14.0	14.0	14.0	14.0	14.0	14.0	14.0	14.0	14.0	14.0	14.0
Colour and Intensity under Long Wave length (365nm)	Blue and high	Blue and high	Green and low	Not detected	Green and high	Green and high	Green and high	Not detected	Green and low	Green and low	Not detected
Colour and Intensity under Short Wave length (254nm)	Blue and high	Blue and high	Green and high	Not detected	Green and high	Green and high	Green and high	Not detected	Green and low	Green and low	Not detected
Colour after spraying with aqueous H ₂ SO ₄	Pink	Pink	Not applicable	Not detected	Green	Green	Greenish-yellow	Not detected	Green	Green	Not detected
Colour after spraying with alcoholic aluminium chloride	Not applicable	Not applicable	Blue	Not detected	Green	Green	Green	Not detected	Green	Green	Not detected

Received for Publication: 05/09/10

Accepted for Publication: 02/10/10

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